

Transitivity System and Meaning in Presidential Election Discourse in Selected Nigerian Online Newspapers (2011- 2019)

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Abstract: Language is an instrument of communication usually deployed by speakers to express their worldview and opinions on every issue, politics not an exception. This study is designed to investigate the representation of public opinions on the Nigerian presidential election results in Nigerian online newspapers, with a view to determining the extent to which meaning is construed and understood in political discourse, especially in presidential election results in Nigerian online newspapers. The ideational meta- function, an aspect of Halliday's (1985) Systemic Functional Grammar that treats the transitivity process is adopted in this study. Six widely read Nigerian online newspapers (Vanguard, Punch, Nigerian Tribune, The Nation, Leadership and The Guardian) published between February and April of the election years in 2011 - 2019 were purposively selected and subjected to linguistic and qualitative method of analysis. The analysis revealed that aspects of the material, mental, and verbal processes feature luxuriantly in explicating opinions and attitudes of people towards the presidential election results in Nigeria.

Keywords: *Transitivity, Public opinions, Presidential election, online newspapers. ideational meta- function.*

INTRODUCTION

Language plays a vital role in revealing people's feelings or attitudes towards a proposition or an issue, political issues are not exempted. Language and politics are interwoven, in politics, language is the tool used for mobilisation and influencing people's decision on political stance. So, Nigerians used language to express their feelings about the political activities before and after the Presidential election results.

Linguistic elements such as transitivity helps to identify the values and attitudes of individuals towards reality in the representations of the speakers' opinion on the election results. As part of the electioneering process, public opinions were expressed in Nigerian newspapers in order to evaluate the election results as being free and fair or otherwise. Modality forms the complement of transitivity, making reference to judgement, observation and attitude in people's expression, and in particular the extent to which a speaker or writer is committed to the point they are making.

Politics is defined by Chilton (20004: p.3) as "a struggle for power, between those who seek to assert and maintain their power and those who seek to resist it..." political organisation is characterised as a great effort made so as to obtain and maintain power and its members. In most cases, politicians, generally, depend on excellent speech making to influence the people that their policies can and should be trusted, and that the people should have faith in them. The procedure of compelling the citizens is what brings language and politics together. This is because language is used by politicians to influence the people's decisions on political matters. As such, language is important to the trade of politicking be it in Nigeria or anywhere else. Those involved actively in

the process of politics are referred to as politicians, and the discourse they engaged in during the process of politicking is political discourse van Dijk, (2006). Language is the most significant tool that politicians use in convincing people; so, language and politics are interwoven. Language and politics convene at the brink of power. Language is a potent weapon, and politics is itself concerned with the use of power Beard, (2000); Adedimeji, (2005). When people get involved in politics; trying so hard to struggle for power in the midst of scarce resources, while trying to convince people to accept their point of view” Adedimeji, (2005:4).

The sustainability of political system is centred on the political organisation. This is the political process which involves electing representatives to occupy leadership position(s) in the country. The political organisation serves as a mediator between the citizens and political parties. Political discourse serves as a tool for persuasion in politics especially, in speeches and campaigns. The media is a channel through which the public are duly informed on political issue, political mobilisation and means of influencing people’s point of view. In lieu of that, the 2011, 2015 and 2019 presidential election results were characterised by different points of view. The 2011 presidential election was peacefully conducted while the people’s reaction to the election results in Nigeria were characterised by violence. The 2015 presidential election results, when an incumbent president was voted out of power, were regarded as the most peaceful and credible election in the political history of Nigeria, and the 2019 presidential election was relatively peaceful.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter explores the underlying concepts of language and politics, media discourse and its importance to the study. It presents a review of related and relevant literature on media discourses, systemic functional, transitivity, political discourses and public opinion. The review, also attempts to juxtapose this research with previous studies, so as to determine area(s) this study has built on and to expand the border of knowledge within the ambits of media, electioneering and political discourse (especially within the Nigerian socio-political domain).

The paper explored the relationship between linguistic structures and culturally constructed meaning in Chinua Achebe’s: *A Man of the people* critically examines the transitivity of proverbs used in the work and is anchored on Halliday’s Systemic Functional Grammar. The analysis revealed that Achebe uses more material processes than relational and verbal processes. The paper concludes that Achebe’s use of varieties of processes, participants and circumstances has made his novel interesting and readable.

Also, Bakare, & Luka. (2004)’s Analysis of the transitivity system of language used in Nigerian newspaper cartoons on Covid 19 Pandemic. The study examined transitivity system of language used in selected online Nigerian Newspapers Cartoons on Covid 19 Pandemic using systemic functional multimodal discourse analysis (SF-MDA) developed by (Djonvou 2005 and O’Holloran, 2008) as approach to the COVID 19 cartoons. The study identified seven (7) processes: material process, mental process, relational process, verbal process, cognitive process, behavioural process and causative process.

STATEMENT OF THE RESEARCH PROBLEM

The use of language remains a powerful tool through which the society influences the decision making process in the country. To this end, extant linguistic studies have investigated issues relating to how ideologies are construed, manipulated and influenced through opinions of the people. Scholars in linguistic and non-linguistic studies have examined news reportage from various conceptual and topical issues (Luu 2016; Osisanwo 2013; Oyeleye & Osisanwo 2013; Scollon, 1998) some previous linguistic studies on political media discourse (Chilton 2004, Bayram, 2010; Taiwo, 2007) have however, focused much attention on how public opinions shape pre-election political debates and speeches in Nigeria. The studies examine how ideology and power are used as manipulative strategies in pre-election political debates and speeches in order to influence people's opinion. Although Taiwo (2007) incorporates to an extent the significance of language used on newspaper headlines as part of political strategy used to influence public opinion. None of these studies addressed how linguistic choices constrain public opinions, especially on Nigerian presidential election results. Osisanwo (2011) also takes into consideration the linguistic techniques (lexical devices and visual forms) through which social actors are represented in the 2003 and 2007 elections in Nigeria. The study however, undermines how public opinion types are contextually determined and necessitated through linguistic devices. This therefore premised the goal of this study which is to investigate transitivity system and meaning in presidential election discourse in selected Nigerian online newspaper linguistic forms. These opinions therefore constitute the data which this study has examined from the linguistic and discourse perspectives.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this study are:

1. to explore transitivity system and meaning in presidential election discourse in selected Nigerian online newspaper linguistic forms.
2. to examine how linguistic features are used to express public opinions in political discourse in Nigeria.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

This study explores how linguistic features are used to express public opinions in political discourse in Nigeria. It addresses political discourse in a real life situation, how different forms and functions of language are used to account for implicit and explicit meaning and relevance in utterances.

This study adds to our understanding of how linguistic components such as transitivity, helps the speaker(s) to use language as the vehicle for the expression of their annotations, thoughts, evaluations, and the bond they set up among themselves and their listeners. By studying the linguistic representations of public opinions on the 2011, 2015 and 2019 presidential elections in the Nigerian online media, language users will understand beyond ordinary meaning the linguistic functions in the representation of public opinions on the 2011, 2015 and 2019 Presidential election results.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Halliday (1979)’s Systemic Functional Grammar (SFG) has two components: systemic grammar and functional grammar. These are two inseparable parts of an integral framework of linguistic theory. Systemic grammar seeks to explain the internal relations in language as a system network, or meaning potential, while functional grammar examines language as a means of social interaction. The theory sees language as organised in a set of systemic clusters, the relation and interrelation of such clusters bring about meaning realisation. Amongst the meta – function, the ideational function construes our world of experience through processes. Through this function, a speaker/writer represents in language experiences of phenomenon in real world, which include experiences, reactions, cognition and perceptions. This ideational function consists of the transitivity system in grammar. In this system, the meaningful grammatical unit is the clause, which expresses what is happening, what is being done, what is felt and what is the state of being. The transitivity system includes six processes: material, mental, relational, behavioural, verbal and existential processes.

METHODOLOGY

Six Nigerian newspapers: The Guardian, The Punch, The Vanguard and Nigerian Tribune, The Nation and Leadership were purposively chosen within the period of February and April 2011 – 2019 a period of electioneering in the country. Related excerpts on the presidential election results were purposively selected and subjected to descriptive analysis.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

Findings and discussion

Transitivity is used for investigating the quality of the ideational metafunction. It presents the basic for recognising the experiential import as articulated in texts.

Some of the verbal processes in our data that explain what has been said about the presidential election results. Also, the verbal process helps in identifying who has said what and what has been said about the presidential election results.

Opinions showing violence and the use of verbal processes

This is the process of saying to reveal peoples’ opinion to the political violence that was erupted in the country after the declaration of the (2011-2019) presidential election results. It typically encompasses three participants: the sayer, the receiver, and the verbiage. The sayer, the responsible for the verbal process, is usually but not essentially conscious. The receiver is the participant to whom the saying is directed. The speakers have adopted different verbal processes to unveil their feelings towards the election results.

Excerpt 1:

I	suggest	Corp members from the South should serve in the South or their states.
sayer	Process: verbal	verbiage

(Punch, April 20, 2011)

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

Excerpt 2:

These disturbances	you	said	are more than mere political protests
	Sayer	process: Verbal	verbiage (quoted)

(*The Nation*, April 19, 2011)

In excerpt 1, 'suggest' is used to represent what is said by the speaker, represented by the first-person pronoun to bring to the fore that corps members should serve their fatherland in their respective states. The speaker opines that the corps members should be given the leverage of serving in their individual state instead of posting them out of their own states to serve. It was on record that many of Nigerian youths, who were serving in the North lost their lives in the post-election violence, which took place in 2011. This almost annulled the purpose of the National Youth Service Corps that is, to encourage national development, integration and promotion of national unity. The speaker deploys the verbalisation process to express their opinions on the post-election violence that emerged in the North. The post-election violence claimed about eight hundred lives and many Nigerians were displaced as a result of the insurrection. Many Nigerians are more susceptible of the risk of residing in the North. One could possibly conclude that the persistence occurrence of riot in the North has created phobia in the hearts of many Nigerians, especially those living in the other parts of the country find it so difficult to live in the Northern part of the country.

Opinions revealing moral decadence and the use of verbal process

Decadence can be viewed as a state of worsening or decay the moral standard, especially due to being exceptionally morally corrupt or self-pity. Moral decadence can be said to mean turn down, decompose and corruption. Political and financial corruption is considered as aspect of moral decadence.

Excerpt 3:

I	say	a loud yes!	the traditional rulers have all embraced politics for it pays them handsomely
Sayer	process: verbal	adjunct/exclamation mark	verbiage (quoted)

(*The Nation*, April 2, 2019)

In excerpt 3, the opinion of the speaker is expressed towards the focus-shift that the traditional rulers have exhibited. They have possibly shortchanged their monarchical responsibilities for political appointment considering the adverb used to modify the verb 'pays'; "the traditional rulers have all embraced politics for it pays handsomely".

Excerpt 4:

He	calls	the 2019 general elections ‘the worst in Nigeria’s history’
Sayer	Process: verbal	verbiage

(*The Nation*, April 12, 2011)

Excerpt 4 reveals that Nigerians are no longer interested in the leadership quality of Buhari. One could possibly conclude that he has not measure up with the moral standard that Nigerians were expecting from him. President Mohammadu Buhari promised to fight corruption, but unfortunately, he has not been able to dutifully carry out the fight against corruption. The verbiage “say” is used to reflect the attitude of Nigerians to the leadership role of President Buhari, his inability to fulfil some of the promises he made to Nigerians.

Opinions showing good moral value with the use of verbal processes in moralistic perspective.

Verbal processes are the processes of saying which are expressed through the verbs such as “said”, “tell”, “promised” “say” and “expressed” to show the opinion of the sayer.

Excerpt 5:

He	promised	the country free and fair election
Sayer	Process: verbal	verbiage

(*Punch*, April 2, 2015)

Also, in excerpt 5, “promised” is used to make reference to the speeches given by Goodluck Jonathan during the 2015 presidential election. Despite the fact that president Good Luck Jonathan was the incumbent president, he went ahead to make an open declaration that there should not be any act of bloodshed in the country. His reaction to the election results was enough to enable Nigerians to realise the truth about politics, it is a game. Obviously, there would be a winner and a loser in any contests whether at the local, state or federal level. The 2015 presidential election result was the first election conducted in Nigeria, which has peacefully unseated the incumbent president. In fact, the positive reaction of president Good luck Jonathan. Jonathan supported his claim that “the blood of Nigerians does not worth his political ambition” Despite his agitation for peaceful co-existence after the announcement of the election results, some people like Orubebe still attempted to disrupt the peace of the country.

Analysis of the relational process

Relational processes deal with the process of being in the world of abstract relations. Relational clauses involve a connection between two separate entities. This relationship is established through copula verbs such as 'be', 'seem', 'become', and 'appear'. Excerpts on relational processes which reflect violence in moralistic perspective are:

Excerpt 6:

It	Is	Particularly worrisome that the violence occurred at a time all Nigerians should be congratulating themselves for successfully holding a presidential election	
Identifier	Process: identifying	Relational	Identified

(The Guardian, April 14, 2011)

Excerpt 7:

It	Is	a bad signal that rather than improvement on their attitudinal over election, politicians are still desperate.	
Identifier	Process: identifying	Relational	Identified

(Leadership, April 15, 2011)

The violence started with the prevalent protests orchestrated by those who own allegiance to the main opposition candidate, President Muhammadu Buhari. The protests degenerated into violent riots or sectarian killings in the Northern states of Adamawa, Bauchi, Bornu, Gombe, Jigawa Kaduna, Katsina, Niger, Sokoto, Yobe and Zamfara. Buhari’s supporters from the North engaged in a clash with the military and police officials. They asserted that the election results were manipulated or rigged. Despite the fact that, the African Union observer team declared the election as the best election ever conducted for decades in Kano, for instances, the ex-president’s posters were set ablaze. In other aforementioned states, there were records of death and some people were displaced. In excerpts 7, the speaker was worried about the negative attitude of politicians to the election results in the country. Nobody was willing to admit defeat among the contestants. The electoral process had been successfully conducted but the election outcome was the bone of contention among the politicians. The speaker opines that the attitude displayed by our political leaders has shown how desperate they are to attain power. This shows that there is little or no improvement in our democratic system. The election must not be a do or die affair rather the politicians involved must imbibe the spirit of sportsmanship.

Mental process that reveal corruption and brutality in moralistic perspective

Excerpt 8:

I	was worried	Not so much by your tone which was a dictate of its circumstance as by its apparent selectivity and dictatorial undertone.
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Senser	Pro: mental	Phenomenon
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(The Punch, March 9, 2011)

Excerpt 9:

I	know for sure	that even if Jesus comes as a man to conduct election in Nigeria because of our nature as bad losers, we will still reject the outcome.
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Senser	Pro: mental	Phenomenon
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(Vanguard, March 8, 2011)

Excerpt 10:

I	Feel	anytime people from the Northern region are killing South-South should be killing the people from Northern region too so their non-regard for human life will stop.
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Senser	Pro: mental	Phenomenon
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(The Nation, March 10, 2011)

The speaker deploys the word “selectivity” in order to show the poor electoral process obtainable in Nigeria. People are supposed to exercise their electoral right by voting for the leaders of their choice but the reverse is the case in Nigeria. The involvement of political fatherism has basterdised our political strength and fundamental human right, since some of the leaders selected to occupy political seat, have little or no genuine passion towards the social welfare of their people at heart, they eventually become dictators and never allow peoples’ view to prevail.

ENGLISH LANGUAGE TEACHING TODAY(ELTT)

In excerpt 10, the speaker is very certain about the nature of Nigerians, especially towards the election results; the people are known for their reluctant nature in accepting the election outcome, most importantly, when it does not favour their party members. They said categorically that, if Jesus being the Messiah, a righteous man who would not compromise his standard for any reason should be saddled with the responsibility of conducting the election in Nigeria, people will still complain of result manipulation. Therefore, it was not surprising that, despite how Prof Attahiru Jega relentlessly worked to conduct an election that was relatively free and fair through the introduction of card readers, people still complained that the election was not free and fair.

In excerpt 10, the speaker perceives high level of social injustice on the part of Southerners living in the Northern part of the country. The speaker used the mental process “feel” to reveal his emotions towards the incessant killing of people from other parts of the country, who are living in the North. From the above excerpts, “Know”, “feel” and “worried” are mental processes realised under the cognition type. The knowledge of the political situation in the country was acquired through the understanding that the speaker has about the political trend in the country.

Existential process

The concept of existence is denoted by certain linguistic elements that serve as symbols for the existence of something. Existential constructions are used to present the fact that something exists or has happened. These constructions present the entity as existing without adding any further information about it. The verb "be" is typically used in these constructions, and they may be introduced by an empty “there” in subject position, which is also referred to as an expletive “there”. Examples of this usage can be found in the following excerpts:

Excerpt 11:

There	Are	millions of questions to be answered and our president Goodluck Jonathan must justify our mandate by ensuring that every drop of bloodshed in the carnage in the North is fully accounted for by instituting an intensive probe of event,
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process: existential	Exists
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(*The Nation*, April 4, 2011)

The excerpt above reflects the happenings in the country. The existential process type is used to state reality of the state of being before, during and after the election had taken place. The process types as revealed in the excerpt indicate how violence disrupted the peace of the country immediately the presidential election results were announced. In excerpt13, the 2011 election was conducted smoothly and regarded to, as the most credible election in the country. The post-election violence initiated the moment president Goodluck Jonathan was declared as the winner. The post-election violence claimed about eight hundred (800) lives and displaced almost sixty-five thousand (65000) people, making the election as the most violent in the Nigeria’s history. The violence erupted by the notion that the Muhammadu Buhari, a northerner, should have won

the election. The speaker opined that the president should probe into the matter and set up commission that would critically examine the factors that led to violence.

Excerpt 12:

There is no mouth or words of the mouth that can explain the injured hearts of parents that lost their wards in the xenophobic rage that took place in the North.

Process: Existent

(Vanguard, April 12, 2011)

There were records of violence in the country, especially in the Northern part. The speaker in excerpt 14, opines that no amount of words can mend the irreparable loss or damage that occurred in their respective families. The pains inflicted on the families of the victims cannot be substituted with money or materials. The speaker compares the violence in the North to the xenophobic rage in the South Africa, which was the killing of foreigners. They believed that people from other aforementioned countries were threat to their economic strength. The Southerners living in the Northern part of Nigeria were killed during the post-election violence, because the winner of the presidential election is from the Southern part of the country. The Northerners have a political affiliation to Mohammadu Buhari, who emerged from the Northern, in order to display their political loyalty towards their leader; they resorted to killing of innocent Nigerians residing in northern he states.

Analysis of material process

Material process involves an action verb, an obligatory entity, and a participant. Material process has an actor and a goal as its participants, and there may be an indication of circumstance.

Material process reflected social responsibility in nationalistic perspective

This is the process of doing something or of something happening, involving an actor and a goal or the target that is affected by the action.

Excerpt 13:

Nigerians	were not	the right to choose	our leaders
	allowed		
Actor	process: material	circumstance	Goal

Excerpt 14:

A country	where the	will be	a team	of educated
	cabinet			patriotic

				competent
				Leaders of integrity
Actor		future tense modal	circumstance	Goal
		process:		
		material		

Excerpt 15:

Nigerians	have proved	to the world that they cannot be perpetually predictable		as a failed nation state
Actor	process: material	circumstantial		Goal

In any democratic nation, the citizens are obliged to perform their civic responsibilities, which include their right to vote for the leader of their choice. Unfortunately, the citizens were deprived of this right of performing their civic responsibility. The speaker, in excerpt 13, uses the noun “Nigerians” as the social actor with the material process “were not allowed” as the process of doing, “the right to choose” as the circumstance and “our leaders” as the goal. In excerpt 14, the speaker believes that those who will be his cabinet members will be people that are intellectually competent to perform the responsibilities they would be saddled with. They must be people of impeccable character. The speaker used “a country” to serve as the social actor with the use of future tense, “a team” as the circumstance and “of educated patriotic competent leaders of integrity” as the goal. In excerpt 15, through the people’s vote, they were able to demonstrate to the whole world that they cannot be referred to as a failed nation again. Nigerians used their votes to vote for the leader of their choice. The right to vote and to be voted for was fully exercised by the citizens, which is their primary responsibility in any democratic country.

SUMMARY

Overall, this study has revealed the manifestation of all the transitivity processes in the opinions of people on the presidential election results. The verbal process is the most predominant process used by the public in their expression of opinions about the outcome of the election. This shows that both president and the people use verbal process of “saying” than any other process to indicate President’s commitment on social and political reforms. The material process of doing expressed by action verbs such as “allowed” “proved” and future tense “will be” characterised by an actor (logical subject) and a goal of the action (a logical direct object), mental process expresses psychological phenomena, with two participants: sensor and the phenomenon. Relational process occurs in two categories: attributive and identifying. Existential constructions are used to present the fact that something exists or has happened

CONCLUSION

The study examined the transitivity processes and how it is manifested in the presidential election results in Nigeria. The transitivity process has shown through verbs action, at which point things are done, specifying who is doing what, how the action is done, and to whom the action is directed. Through this process of transitivity, the study determines from the text the person that has carried out specific actions and their intentions. These actions and intentions in turn build up the way consumer of media information perceive the outcome of the election in the country. The intention of framing such reports with the transitivity processes is a deliberate strategy to reflect whether the presidential election results is fair or otherwise.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The focus of this study is representation of public opinions on Nigerian presidential election results in selected Nigerian online newspapers. The study gathered data from print media. Hence, it recommends that researchers could investigate on how linguistic functions in public opinions on the (2011-2023) presidential election results are represented on different social media platforms.

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